

Neutrosophic Generalized Semi Closed Sets In Neutrosophic Topological Spaces

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Abstract- F.Smarandache introduced and developed the concept of Neutrosophic set from the fuzzy sets and intuitionistic fuzzy sets. A.A. Salama introduced Neutrosophic topological spaces by using the Neutrosophic crisp sets. Aim of this paper is we introduced and studied about Neutrosophic generalized semi closed sets in Neutrosophic topological spaces and its properties are discussed details

Index Terms- Neutrosophic semi closed sets, Neutrosophic semi open sets, Neutrosophic generalized semi closed sets, Neutrosophic generalized semi open sets

1. INTRODUCTION

Topology is a classical subjects, as a generalization topological spaces many type of topological spaces introduced over the year. C.L. Chang[2] was introduced and developed fuzzy topological space by using L.A. Zadeh's[14] fuzzy sets. Coker[5] introduced the notion of Intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces by using Atanassov's[1] intuitionistic fuzzy set

Neutrality the degree of indeterminacy, as an independent concept, was introduced by Smarandache [8] in 1998. He also defined the Neutrosophic set on three component Neutrosophic topological spaces $(t, f, i) = (\text{Truth, Falsehood, Indeterminacy})$, The Neutrosophic crisp set concept was converted to Neutrosophic topological spaces by Salama [12] et al.

R.Dhavaseelan[4], Saied Jafari are introduced Neutrosophic generalized closed sets. K. Bageerathi [10] et al introduced and studied about Neutrosophic semi closed sets in Neutrosophic topological spaces. In this paper we introduced and studied about Neutrosophic generalized semi closed sets in Neutrosophic topological spaces and its properties are discussed details

2. PRELIMINARIES

In this section, we introduce the basic definition for Neutrosophic sets and its operation.

Definition 2.1 [9]

Let X be a non-empty fixed set. A Neutrosophic set A is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$$

where $\mu_A(x)$, $\sigma_A(x)$ and $\gamma_A(x)$ which represent Neutrosophic topological spaces the degree of membership function, the degree indeterminacy and the degree of non-membership function respectively of each element $x \in X$ to the set A .

Remark 2.2 [9]

A Neutrosophic set

$$A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$$

can be identified to an ordered triple $\langle \mu_A, \sigma_A, \gamma_A \rangle$ in $] -0, 1+[$ on X .

Remark 2.3[9]

we shall use the symbol

$$A = \langle x, \mu_A, \sigma_A, \gamma_A \rangle \text{ for the Neutrosophic set}$$

$$A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}.$$

Example 2.4 [9]

Every Intuitionistic fuzzy set A is a non-empty set in X is obviously on Neutrosophic set having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), 1 - (\mu_A(x) + \gamma_A(x)), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}.$$

Since our main purpose is to construct the tools for developing Neutrosophic set and Neutrosophic topology, we must introduce the Neutrosophic set

0_N and 1_N in X as follows:

0_N may be defined as :

$$(0_1) 0_N = \{ \langle x, 0, 0, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(0_2) 0_N = \{ \langle x, 0, 1, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(0_3) 0_N = \{ \langle x, 0, 1, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(0_4) 0_N = \{ \langle x, 0, 0, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

1_N may be defined as :

$$(1_1) 1_N = \{ \langle x, 1, 0, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(1_2) 1_N = \{ \langle x, 1, 0, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(1_3) 1_N = \{ \langle x, 1, 1, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(1_4) 1_N = \{ \langle x, 1, 1, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

Definition 2.5 [9]

Let $A = \langle \mu_A, \sigma_A, \gamma_A \rangle$ be a Neutrosophic set on X , then the complement of the set A

[$C(A)$ for short] defined as

$$C(A) = \{ \langle x, \gamma_A(x), 1 - \sigma_A(x), \mu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$$

Definition 2.6 [9]

Let x be a non-empty set, and Neutrosophic sets A and B in the form

$$A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \text{ and}$$

$$B = \{ \langle x, \mu_B(x), \sigma_B(x), \gamma_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}.$$

Then we consider definition for subsets ($A \subseteq B$).

$A \subseteq B$ defined as :

$$A \subseteq B \Leftrightarrow \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \leq \sigma_B(x) \text{ and} \\ \gamma_A(x) \geq \gamma_B(x) \text{ for all } x \in X$$

Proposition 2.7 [9]

For any Neutrosophic set A , then the following condition are holds :

(i) $0_N \subseteq A, 0_N \subseteq 0_N$

(ii) $A \subseteq 1_N, 1_N \subseteq 1_N$

Definition 2.8 [9]

Let X be a non-empty set, and

$$A = \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle,$$

$$B = \langle x, \mu_B(x), \sigma_B(x), \gamma_B(x) \rangle \text{ are Neutrosophic sets.}$$

Then

(i) $A \cap B$ defined as :

$$A \cap B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \vee \sigma_B(x), \gamma_A(x) \vee \gamma_B(x) \rangle$$

(ii) $A \cup B$ defined as :

$$A \cup B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \vee \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_B(x), \gamma_A(x) \wedge \gamma_B(x) \rangle$$

Definition 2.9 [9]

We can easily generalize the operation of intersection and union in Definition 2.8 to arbitrary family of Neutrosophic sets as follows :

Let $\{ A_j : j \in J \}$ be a arbitrary family of Neutrosophic sets in X , then

(i) $\cap A_j$ defined as :

$$\cap A_j = \langle x, \bigwedge_{j \in J} \mu_{A_j}(x), \bigwedge_{j \in J} \sigma_{A_j}(x), \bigvee_{j \in J} \gamma_{A_j}(x) \rangle$$

(ii) $\cup A_j$ defined as : $\cup A_j = \langle x, \bigvee, \bigwedge, \bigwedge \rangle$

Proposition 2.10 [9]

For all A and B are two Neutrosophic sets then the following condition are true :

(1) $C(A \cap B) = C(A) \cup C(B)$

(2) $C(A \cup B) = C(A) \cap C(B)$.

Definition 2.11 [11,12]

A Neutrosophic topology is a non -empty set X is a family τ_N of Neutrosophic subsets in X satisfying the following axioms :

(i) $0_N, 1_N \in \tau_N$,

(ii) $G_1 \cap G_2 \in \tau_N$ for any $G_1, G_2 \in \tau_N$,

(iii) $\cup G_i \in \tau_N$ for every $\{ G_i : i \in J \} \subseteq \tau_N$

the pair (X, τ_N) is called a Neutrosophic topological space.

The element Neutrosophic topological spaces of τ_N are called Neutrosophic open sets.

A Neutrosophic set F is closed if and only if $C(F)$ is Neutrosophic open.

Example 2.14 [11,12]

Let $X = \{ x \}$ and

$$A_1 = \{ \langle x, 0.6, 0.6, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$A_2 = \{ \langle x, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$A_3 = \{ \langle x, 0.6, 0.7, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$A_4 = \{ \langle x, 0.5, 0.6, 0.9 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

Then the family $\tau_N = \{ 0_N, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4, 1_N \}$ is called a Neutrosophic topological space on X .

Definition 2.15 [11,12] Let (X, τ_N) be Neutrosophic topological spaces and

$$A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$$

be a Neutrosophic set in X .

Then the Neutrosophic closure and Neutrosophic interior of A are defined by

$$\text{Neu-Cl}(A) = \cap \{ K : K \text{ is a Neutrosophic closed set} \\ \text{in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq K \}$$

$$\text{Neu-Int}(A) = \cup \{ G : G \text{ is a Neutrosophic open set} \\ \text{in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A \}.$$

Definition 2.16 [11,12]

(i) A is Neutrosophic open set if and only if

$$A = \text{Neu-Int}(A).$$

(ii) A is Neutrosophic closed set if and only if

$$A = \text{Neu-Cl}(A).$$

Proposition 2.17 [11,12]

For any Neutrosophic set A in (X, τ_N) we have

(i) $\text{Neu-Cl}(C(A)) = C(\text{Neu-Int}(A))$,

(ii) $\text{Neu-Int}(C(A)) = C(\text{Neu-Cl}(A))$.

Proposition 2.18 [11,12]

Let (X, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topological spaces and A, B be two Neutrosophic sets in X . Then the following properties are holds :

(i) $\text{Neu-Int}(A) \subseteq A$,

(ii) $A \subseteq \text{Neu-Cl}(A)$,

(iii) $A \subseteq B \Rightarrow \text{Neu-Int}(A) \subseteq \text{Neu-Int}(B)$,

(iv) $A \subseteq B \Rightarrow \text{Neu-Cl}(A) \subseteq \text{Neu-Cl}(B)$,

(v) $\text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-Int}(A)) = \text{Neu-Int}(A)$,

(vi) $\text{Neu-Cl}(\text{Neu-Cl}(A)) = \text{Neu-Cl}(A)$,

(vii) $\text{Neu-Int}(A \cap B) = \text{Neu-Int}(A) \cap \text{Neu-Int}(B)$,

(viii) $\text{Neu-Cl}(A \cup B) = \text{Neu-Cl}(A) \cup \text{Neu-Cl}(B)$,

(ix) $\text{Neu-Int}(0_N) = 0_N$,

(x) $\text{Neu-Int}(1_N) = 1_N$,

(xi) $\text{Neu-Cl}(0_N) = 0_N$,

(xii) $\text{Neu-Cl}(1_N) = 1_N$,

(xiii) $A \subseteq B \Rightarrow C(B) \subseteq C(A)$,

(xiv) $\text{Neu-Cl}(A \cap B) \subseteq \text{Neu-Cl}(A) \cap \text{Neu-Cl}(B)$,

(xv) $\text{Neu-Int}(A \cup B) \supseteq \text{Neu-Int}(A) \cup \text{Neu-Int}(B)$.

Definition:2.19 [10]

A subset A of a Neutrosophic space (X, τ_N) is called Neutrosophic semi-open

if $A \subseteq \text{Neu-Cl}(\text{Neu-int}(A))$.

The complement of Neutrosophic semi-open set is called Neutrosophic semi-closed.

Definition 2.20 [4]

Let A be a subset of a Neutrosophic space (X, τ_N) is called generalized Neutrosophic closed (Neu g-closed) if $\text{Neu-cl}A \subseteq U$, whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is Neu-open.

The complement of a Neu g- closed set is called the Neu g-open set.

3. NEUTROSOPHIC GENERALIZED SEMI CLOSED SET IN NEUTROSOPHIC TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

In this section, we introduce the Neutrosophic generalized semi closed set in Neutrosophic topological spaces

Definition 3.1

Let A be a subset of a Neutrosophic space (X, τ_N) is called Neutrosophic generalized semi closed (Neu-GS-closed) if Neutrosophic semi-cl $A \subseteq U$, whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is Neutrosophic open.

The complement of a Neu-GS-closed set is called the Neu-GS-open set.

Example 3.2

Let $X = \{ a, b \}$ and

$$A_1 = \langle (0.4, 0.6, 0.5), (0.7, 0.3, 0.6) \rangle$$

$$A_2 = \langle (0.3, 0.7, 0.8), (0.6, 0.4, 0.2) \rangle$$

$$A_3 = \langle (0.4, 0.7, 0.5), (0.7, 0.4, 0.2) \rangle$$

$$A_4 = \langle (0.3, 0.6, 0.8), (0.6, 0.3, 0.6) \rangle .$$

Then $\tau_N = \{ 0_N, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4, 1_N \}$

is Neutrosophic topological spaces on X .

Now, $A_5 = \langle (0.5, 0.7, 0.5), (0.9, 0.4, 0.5) \rangle$ is Neutrosophic generalized semi closed set

Definition 3.3

Let (X, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topological spaces .

Then for a Neutrosophic subset A of X , the Neutrosophic semi-interior of A is the union of all Neutrosophic semi-open sets of X contained in A . i.e. $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)$

$$= \cup \{ G : G \text{ is a Neu-GS open set in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A \} .$$

Proposition 3.4

Neutrosophic subsets A and B of a Neutrosophic topological spaces X we have

$$(i) \text{ Neu-GS-Int}(A) \subseteq A$$

$$(ii) A \text{ is Neu-GS-open set in } X \Leftrightarrow \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) = A$$

$$(iii) \text{ Neu-GS-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)) = \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)$$

$$(iv) \text{ If } A \subseteq B \text{ then } \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Int}(B)$$

Proof:

(i) follows from Definition 3.3.

Let A be Neu-GS-open set in X . Then $A \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)$. By using (i) we get $A = \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)$.

Conversely assume that $A = \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)$. By using Definition 3.3, A is Neu-GS-open set in X . Thus (ii) is proved. By using (ii), $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)) = \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)$. This proves (iii). Since $A \subseteq B$, by using (i), $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \subseteq A \subseteq B$. That is $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \subseteq B$. By (iii), $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Int}(B)$. Thus $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Int}(B)$. This proves (iv).

Theorem 3.5

Let (X, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topological spaces . Then for any Neutrosophic subset A and B of a Neutrosophic topological spaces , we have

$$(i) \text{ Neu-GS-Int}(A \cap B) = \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \cap \text{Neu-GS-Int}(B)$$

$$(ii) \text{ Neu-GS-Int}(A \cup B) \supseteq \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \cup \text{Neu-GS-Int}(B)$$

Proof : Since $A \cap B \subseteq A$ and $A \cap B \subseteq B$, by using Proposition 3.4(iv), $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A \cap B) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)$ and $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A \cap B) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Int}(B)$. This implies that $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A \cap B) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \cap \text{Neu-GS-Int}(B)$ -----(1).

By using Proposition 3.4(i), $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \subseteq A$ and $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(B) \subseteq B$. This implies that $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \cap \text{Neu-GS-Int}(B) \subseteq A \cap B$. Now applying Proposition 3.4(iv), $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \cap \text{Neu-GS-Int}(B)) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A \cap B)$. By (1), $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \cap \text{Neu-GS-Int}(B)) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A \cap B)$. By Proposition 3.2(iii), $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \cap \text{Neu-GS-Int}(B) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A \cap B)$ -----(2).

From (1) and (2), $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A \cap B) = \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \cap \text{Neu-GS-Int}(B)$. This implies (i). Since $A \subseteq A \cup B$ and $B \subseteq A \cup B$, by using Proposition 3.4(iv), $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A \cup B)$ and $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(B) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A \cup B)$. This implies that $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \cup \text{Neu-GS-Int}(B) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Int}(A \cup B)$. Hence (ii).

The following example shows that the equality need not be hold in Theorem 3.5(ii).

Example 3.6

Let $X = \{ a, b, c \}$ and $\tau_N = \{ 0_N, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4, 1_N \}$ where

$$A_1 = \langle (0.41, 0.71, 0.11), (0.51, 0.61, 0.21), (0.91, 0.71, 0.31) \rangle,$$

$$A_2 = \langle (0.41, 0.61, 0.11), (0.71, 0.71, 0.21), (0.91, 0.51, 0.11) \rangle,$$

$$A_3 = \langle (0.41, 0.71, 0.11), (0.71, 0.71, 0.21), (0.91, 0.71, 0.11) \rangle,$$

$$A_4 = \langle (0.41, 0.61, 0.11), (0.51, 0.61, 0.21), (0.91, 0.51, 0.31) \rangle.$$

Then (X, τ_N) is a Neutrosophic topological spaces.

Consider the Neutrosophic sets are

$$E = \langle (0.71, 0.61, 0.11), (0.71, 0.61, 0.11), (0.91, 0.51, 0.01) \rangle \text{ and}$$

$$F = \langle (0.41, 0.61, 0.11), (0.51, 0.71, 0.21), (2.1, 0.71, 0.11) \rangle.$$

Then $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(E) = D$ and $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(F) = D$. This implies that $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(E) \cup \text{Neu-GS-Int}(F) = D$.

Now,

$$E \cup F = \langle (0.71, 0.61, 0.11), (0.71, 0.71, 0.11), (2.01, 0.71, 0.01) \rangle,$$

it follows that $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(E \cup F) = B$. Then $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(E \cup F) \not\subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Int}(E) \cup \text{Neu-GS-Int}(F)$.

4. NEUTROSOPHIC GENERALIZED SEMI-CLOSURE IN NEUTROSOPHIC TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

In this section, we introduce the concept of Neutrosophic generalized semi closure operators in a Neutrosophic topological spaces.

Definition 4.1

Let (X, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topological spaces. Then for a Neutrosophic subset A of X .

The Neutrosophic semi-closure of A is the intersection of all Neutrosophic generalized semi closed sets of X contained in A . That is,
 $Neu-GS-Cl(A)$

$$= \bigcap \{ K : K \text{ is a Neu-GS-C set in } X \text{ and } K \supseteq A \}.$$

Proposition 4.2

Let (X, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topological spaces. Then for any Neutrosophic subsets A of X ,

(i) $C(Neu-GS-Int(A)) = Neu-GS-Cl(C(A)),$

(ii) $C(Neu-GS-Cl(A)) = Neu-GS-Int(C(A)).$

Proof :

By using Definition 3.3,

$Neu-GS-Int(A) = \bigcup \{ G : G \text{ is a Neu-GS-open set in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A \}$. Taking complement on both sides,
 $C(Neu-GS-Int(A)) = C(\bigcup \{ G : G \text{ is a Neu-GS open set in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A \}) = \bigcap \{ C(G) : C(G) \text{ is a Neu-GS-C set in } X \text{ and } C(A) \subseteq C(G) \}$. Replacing $C(G)$ by K , we get
 $C(Neu-GS-Int(A)) = \bigcap \{ K : K \text{ is a Neu-GS-C set in } X \text{ and } K \supseteq C(A) \}$. By Definition 4.1, $C(Neu-GS-Int(A)) = Neu-GS-Cl(C(A))$. This proves(i). By using(i),
 $C(Neu-GS-Int(C(A))) = Neu-GS-Cl(C(C(A))) = Neu-GS-Cl(A)$. Taking complement on both sides, we get
 $Neu-GS-Int(C(A)) = C(Neu-GS-Cl(A))$.

Hence proved(ii)

Proposition 4.3

Let (X, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topological spaces .

Then for any Neutrosophic subsets A and B of a Neutrosophic topological spaces X we have

(i) $A \subseteq Neu-GS-Cl(A)$

(ii) $A \text{ is Neu-GS-C set in } X \Leftrightarrow Neu-GS-Cl(A) = A$

(iii) $Neu-GS-Cl(Neu-GS-Cl(A)) = Neu-GS-Cl(A)$

(iv) If $A \subseteq B$ then $Neu-GS-Cl(A) \subseteq Neu-GS-Cl(B)$

Proof :

(i) follows from Definition 4.2.

Let A be Neu-GS-closed set in X . By using Proposition 4.3, $C(A)$ is Neu-GS-open set in X . By Proposition 4.2(ii), $Neu-GS-Int(C(A)) = C(A) \Leftrightarrow C(Neu-GS-Cl(A)) = C(A) \Leftrightarrow Neu-GS-Cl(A) = A$. Thus proved(ii). By using(ii), $Neu-GS-Cl(Neu-GS-Cl(A)) = Neu-GS-Cl(A)$. This proves(iii). Since $A \subseteq B, C(B) \subseteq C(A)$. By using Proposition 3.4(iv), $Neu-GS-Int(C(B)) \subseteq Neu-GS-Int(C(A))$. Taking complement on both sides, $C(Neu-GS-Int(C(B))) \supseteq C(Neu-GS-Int(C(A)))$. By Proposition 4.2(ii), $Neu-GS-Cl(A) \subseteq Neu-GS-Cl(B)$. This proves(iv).

Proposition 4.4

Let A be a Neutrosophic set in a Neutrosophic topological spaces X . Then $Neu-Int(A) \subseteq Neu-GS-Int(A) \subseteq A \subseteq Neu-GS-Cl(A) \subseteq Neu-Cl(A)$.

Proof :

It follows from the definitions of corresponding operators

Proposition 4.5

Let (X, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topological spaces .

Then for a Neutrosophic subset A and B of a Neutrosophic topological spaces X , we have

(i) $Neu-GS-Cl(A \cup B) = Neu-GS-Cl(A) \cup Neu-GS-Cl(B)$ and

(ii) $Neu-GS-Cl(A \cap B) \subseteq Neu-GS-Cl(A) \cap Neu-GS-Cl(B)$.

Proof :

Since $Neu-GS-Cl(A \cup B) = Neu-GS-Cl(C(C(A \cup B)))$,

By using Proposition 4.2(i), $Neu-GS-Cl(A \cup B) = C(Neu-GS-Int(C(A \cup B))) = C(Neu-GS-Int(C(A) \cap C(B)))$.

Again using Proposition 3.5(i), $Neu-GS-Cl(A \cup B) = C(Neu-GS-Int(C(A)) \cap Neu-GS-Int(C(B))) = C(Neu-GS-Int(C(A))) \cup C(Neu-GS-Int(C(B)))$. By using

Proposition 4.2(i), $Neu-GS-Cl(A \cup B) = Neu-GS-Cl(C(C(A))) \cup Neu-GS-Cl(C(C(B))) = Neu-GS-Cl(A) \cup Neu-GS-Cl(B)$. Thus proved(i). Since $A \cap B \subseteq A$ and $A \cap B \subseteq B$, by using Proposition 4.3(iv),

$Neu-GS-Cl(A \cap B) \subseteq Neu-GS-Cl(A)$ and $Neu-GS-Cl(A \cap B) \subseteq Neu-GS-Cl(B)$. This implies that $Neu-GS-Cl(A \cap B) \subseteq Neu-GS-Cl(A) \cap Neu-GS-Cl(B)$. This proves(ii).

The following example shows that the equality need not be hold in Proposition 4.5(ii).

Example 4.6

Let $X = \{ a, b, c \}$ with $\tau_N = \{ 0_N, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4, 1_N \}$ and

$C(\tau_N) = \{ 1_N, A_5, A_6, A_7, A_8, 0_N \}$ where

$A_1 = \langle (0.5, 0.6, 0.1), (0.6, 0.7, 0.1), (0.9, 0.5, 0.2) \rangle$

$A_2 = \langle (0.4, 0.5, 0.2), (0.8, 0.6, 0.3), (0.9, 0.7, 0.3) \rangle$

$A_3 = \langle (0.4, 0.5, 0.2), (0.6, 0.6, 0.3), (0.9, 0.5, 0.3) \rangle$

$A_4 = \langle (0.5, 0.6, 0.1), (0.8, 0.7, 0.1), (0.9, 0.7, 0.2) \rangle$

$A_5 = \langle (0.1, 0.4, 0.5), (0.1, 0.3, 0.6), (0.2, 0.5, 0.9) \rangle$,

$A_6 = \langle (0.2, 0.5, 0.4), (0.3, 0.4, 0.8), (0.3, 0.3, 0.9) \rangle$,

$A_7 = \langle (0.2, 0.5, 0.4), (0.3, 0.4, 0.6), (0.3, 0.5, 0.9) \rangle$,

$A_8 = \langle (0.1, 0.4, 0.5), (0.1, 0.3, 0.8), (0.2, 0.3, 0.9) \rangle$.

Then (X, τ_N) is a Neutrosophic topological spaces.

Consider the Neutrosophic sets are

$A_9 = \langle (0.1, 0.2, 0.5), (0.2, 0.3, 0.7), (0.3, 0.3, 1) \rangle$ and

$A_{10} = \langle (0.2, 0.4, 0.8), (0.1, 0.2, 0.8), (0.2, 0.5, 0.9) \rangle$.

Then $Neu-GS-Cl(A_9) = A_7$ and $Neu-GS-Cl(A_{10}) = A_7$.

This implies that $Neu-GS-Cl(A_9) \cap Neu-GS-Cl(A_{10}) = A_7$. Now, $A_9 \cap A_{10} = \langle (0.1, 0.2, 0.8), (0.1, 0.2, 0.8), (0.2, 0.3, 1) \rangle$, it follows that $Neu-GS-Cl(A_9 \cap A_{10}) = A_8$.

Then $Neu-GS-Cl(A_9) \cap Neu-GS-Cl(A_{10}) \not\subseteq Neu-GS-Cl(A_9 \cap A_{10})$.

Theorem 4.7

Let (X, τ_N) be a NTS. Then for a Neutrosophic subset A and B of X we have

(i) $Neu-GS-Cl(A) \supseteq A \cup Neu-GS-Cl(Neu-GS-Int(A))$,

(ii) $Neu-GS-Int(A) \subseteq A \cap Neu-GS-Int(Neu-GS-Cl(A))$,

(iii) $Neu-Int(Neu-GS-Cl(A)) \subseteq Neu-Int(Neu-Cl(A))$,

(iv) $Neu-Int(Neu-GS-Cl(A)) \supseteq Neu-Int(Neu-GS-Cl(Neu-GS-Int(A)))$.

Proof :

By Proposition 4.3(i), $A \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A)$ ---(1). Again using Proposition 3.4(i), $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \subseteq A$. Then $\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A)$,(2).

By(1) &(2) we have, $A \cup \text{Neu-GS-Cl}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A)$. This proves(i).

By Proposition 3.4(i), $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \subseteq A$ -----(3).

Again using proposition 4.3(i), $A \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A)$. Then $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A))$ --(4). From(3) &(4), we have $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \subseteq A \cap \text{Neu-GS-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A))$. This proves(ii).

By Proposition 4.4, $\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A) \subseteq \text{Neu-Cl}(A)$. We get $\text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A)) \subseteq \text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-Cl}(A))$. Hence(iii). By(i), $\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A) \supseteq A \cup \text{Neu-GS-Cl}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A))$. We have $\text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A)) \supseteq \text{Neu-Int}(A \cup \text{Neu-GS-Cl}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)))$. Since $\text{Neu-Int}(A \cup B) \supseteq \text{Neu-Int}(A) \cup \text{Neu-Int}(B)$, $\text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A)) \supseteq \text{Neu-Int}(A) \cup \text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A))) \supseteq \text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)))$.

Hence(iv).

Theorem 4.8

Let (X, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topological spaces.

Then for a Neutrosophic subset A and B of X we have,

- (i) $\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A) \supseteq A \cup \text{Neu-GS-Cl}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A))$,
- (ii) $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \subseteq A \cap \text{Neu-GS-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A))$,
- (iii) $\text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A)) \subseteq \text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-Cl}(A))$,
- (iv) $\text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A)) \supseteq \text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)))$.

Proof:

By Proposition 4.3(i), $A \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A)$ -----(1).

Again using Proposition 3.4(i), $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \subseteq A$. Then $\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A)$ --(2)

By(1)&(2) we have, $A \cup \text{Neu-GS-Cl}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A)$. This proves(i). By Proposition 3.4(i), $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \subseteq A$ -----(1). Again using proposition 4.3(i), $A \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A)$. Then $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \subseteq \text{Neu-GS-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A))$ -----(2).

From(1) &(2), we have $\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A) \subseteq A \cap \text{Neu-GS-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A))$. This proves(ii). By Proposition 4.4, $\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A) \subseteq \text{Neu-Cl}(A)$. We get $\text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A)) \subseteq \text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-Cl}(A))$. Hence(iii). By(i), $\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A) \supseteq A \cup \text{Neu-GS-Cl}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A))$. We have $\text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A)) \supseteq \text{Neu-Int}(A \cup \text{Neu-GS-Cl}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)))$. Since $\text{Neu-Int}(A \cup B) \supseteq \text{Neu-Int}(A) \cup \text{Neu-Int}(B)$, $\text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(A)) \supseteq \text{Neu-Int}(A) \cup \text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A))) \supseteq \text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-GS-Cl}(\text{Neu-GS-Int}(A)))$. Hence(iv).

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